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Effect Of Reward And Motivation On Organizational Performance Of Tertiary Institutions In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the effect of reward and motivation on organizational Performance of tertiary institutions in Anambra state. The researcher developed two objectives such as to: Determine the effect of reward on Organizational Performance of selected tertiary institutions in Anambra state Nigeria; Identify the effect of motivation on Organizational Performance of selected tertiary institutions in Anambra state Nigeria. The research design used for this study was descriptive survey research design study adopted for this study. This enabled the researcher to generate first hand data for the study and for the test of hypotheses. The sources of data for this research were mainly primary data and secondary data. The total population for the study is fifty-seven thousand and seven hundred and ten students. (57, 710), While 369 sample size were gotten using taro Yamane guidelines. The findings of the study revealed that Reward has significant effect on Organizational Performance of tertiary institution in Anambra state. T-statistics of 2.996 and probability value of 0.006. Motivation has significant effect on Organizational Performance of tertiary institution in Anambra state. T-statistics of 3.453 and probability value of 0.000. The study recommends; The study also recommends that management should provide effective incentive plan to their employees from time to time to boost their morale for enhanced productivity and performance. The reason is that bonuses will encourage them to put more effort in discharging their duties effectively. Management should do well to adopt on the spot praise as a medium for recognition and appreciation for hard work for promptness equal effectiveness.

Keywords: Reward, motivation, organizational Performance, and tertiary institutions

1.1. INTRODUCTION

Organizational performance in tertiary institutions is largely determined by the quality, commitment, and productivity of employees who drive teaching, research, and administrative functions. In today's competitive educational environment, rewards and motivation have become essential tools for enhancing employee performance and institutional effectiveness (Nwangwu, Ohanyere, Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025).. Rewards both financial and non-financial serve as tangible recognition of employees' efforts, while motivation provides the internal drive that inspires them to achieve organizational goals (Ifechukwu-jacobs, & Atueyi, 2024). In many tertiary institutions in Anambra State, issues such as inadequate remuneration, poor welfare packages, and lack of recognition have contributed to low morale, absenteeism, and reduced productivity among staff. Consequently, there is a growing need to assess how effective reward systems and motivational strategies can improve employee commitment, efficiency, and overall organizational performance (Ifechukwu-Jacobs, Arinze, & Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025). This study

therefore investigates the effect of rewards and motivation on organizational performance of tertiary institutions in Anambra State, aiming to determine how well-structured incentives and motivation can foster better outcomes, innovation, and institutional growth. Despite the crucial role tertiary institutions play in the socio-economic and educational development of Anambra State, many of them continue to face challenges related to low staff morale, poor commitment, and declining productivity (Onya, Arinze, & Atueyi, 2025). These problems are often linked to inadequate reward systems and ineffective motivational strategies. In many cases, employees are not properly recognized or compensated for their efforts, leading to dissatisfaction, high turnover, and poor service delivery. Furthermore, irregular payment of salaries, limited career advancement opportunities, and lack of non-monetary incentives such as recognition and training have weakened employees' drive to perform optimally. As a result, institutional goals such as academic excellence, research productivity, and administrative efficiency are not fully achieved (Ohanyere Arinze, & Atueyi 2025). This situation raises the question of whether the existing reward and motivation practices in tertiary institutions in Anambra State are sufficient to enhance organizational performance. Therefore, this study seeks to examine the effect of rewards and motivation on the organizational performance of tertiary institutions in Anambra State.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

The broad objective is to evaluate the effect of reward and motivation on organizational Performance of tertiary institutions in Anambra state. The specific objectives of this study include:

- i. Examine the effect of reward on Organizational Performance of selected tertiary institutions in Anambra state Nigeria
- ii. Investigate the effect of motivation on Organizational Performance of selected tertiary institutions in Anambra state Nigeria

1.3 Statement of Hypotheses

This study is guided by the following hypotheses:

H₀₃: Reward has no significant effect on Organizational Performance of selected tertiary institutions in Anambra State Nigeria

H₀: Motivation has no significant effect on Organizational Performance of selected tertiary institutions in Anambra State Nigeria

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1. Conceptual framework

2.1.1 Reward

Reward exists in order to motivate employees to work towards achieving strategic goals which are set by the entities. Armstrong (as cited in Anku, Amewugach & Glover 2018) 'said that' reward systems consist of the interested processes and practices which combine to ensure that the reward management is carried out effectively to the benefit of the organization and the people who work there'' it is based on the reward strategy, which are derived from business strategy. This strategy coordinates and controls the operation and advancement of reward practices, process and thus, shape policies that involves reward management which in turn influence reward practices, process and procedures (Anku, et al 2018)

Robert (2015) defined reward system as the process of developing and implementing strategies, policies and systems which help the organization to achieve its objectives by obtaining and keeping the people it needs and increasing their motivation and commitment. Johnson et al (2019) outlines the aims of reward system to include attract, retain and motivate employee, to support the attainment of the organization's strategic and short-term objectives by helping to ensure that it has the skilled, competent, committed and well motivated work force it needs, to meet the expectations of employees that they will be treated equitably, fairly and consistently in relation to the work they do and their contribution. Neckermann and Kosfeld (2018) draw a distinction between two basic types of rewards namely: Intrinsic rewards and extrinsic rewards. Intrinsic Rewards: Intrinsic rewards often called non-financial rewards are inherent of an activity and their administrative are not dependent upon the presence or actions of any other person or thing. Intrinsic is concerned about the feeling of being recognized, praised for a job well done and

participation in whatever we do. Extrinsic rewards do not follow naturally or inherently from the performance of an activity but are administered to a person by some external agents. Extrinsic reward concerns such motivations like money, retirement benefits, health insurance scheme, compensation, salary and bonus.

2.1.2 Motivation

Studying motivation, as noted by (Armstrong, 2019) is an integral part of human resource management. They point out that motivation focuses on reasons that explain the way people behave. As (Price, 2019) points out, all managers should address themselves to issues of employee motivation. He concludes that the life span of organisations depend very much on their ability to achieve personal and organisational goals. Saari and Judge, (2017) confirm the issue of needs or motives. These scholars contend that our behaviour as human beings is “goal-seeking”. (Armstrong, 2018) agrees that indeed motivation is goal directed behaviour. Robbins et al.,(2019) also concur and argue that motives direct the way employees behave at the work place. This point is also highlighted by Price, 2017 who confirms that motivation energizes, directs and sustains behaviour. Motivation is a great contributor to the extent of employee commitment. They also argue that motivation cannot be in isolation, it must go hand in hand with, among other things, learning and ability.

According to Robbins, et al.,(2017) future leaders ought to be selected on the basis of their ability to stimulate organisational motivation. It is, therefore, very important, for organisations to take the issue of motivation seriously in administration of reward systems because job satisfaction or lack of it affects productivity and the achievement of organisational goals. Saari and Judge, (2017) note that, the force that is behind motivation drives employees to act and put in willingly their best performance towards the achievement of expected results. Managers therefore need to understand the needs and aspirations of their employees. Reward systems can motivate or demotivate employees. They argue that managers must know what motivates employees so as to bring about improvement in job performance and go further to argue that where employees goals are not met (and organizational goals are not in conformity with personal goals of employees), employees may not identify themselves with organisation goals. As a consequence, organisational goals may be put in jeopardy. Employees to perform cannot be overemphasized. (Saari and Judge, 2017) point out that rewards are vital for staff acquisition and retention. Promotion is necessary for job satisfaction and that it stands for increased incentives in recognition of the employee’s performance and contribution. Career advancement and reward systems are sources of motivation at the work place.

2.2. Theoretical framework

Self-concept Theory of Career Development

Super’s Self-concept Theory of Career Development has relatively gained more currency among several other theories of career choice and development, not only in the USA but across the globe. Super (1969, 1980, 1990) submit that an individual’s choice of career and development is basically a process of developing and implementing ones opinion of self. Super (1990), opines that self-concept arises from an interplay of “physical and mental growth, personal experiences, and environmental characteristics and stimulation”. Although Super argue that the process of development and maturation is essentially organic, contemporary thought (Savickas, 2018) of Super’s model have highlighted the need to include the influence of social and environmental factors during the development of an individual’s self-concept. In extending Super’s work, Savickas (2018) introduced a constructivist view and stated that “the process of career construction is essentially that of developing and implementing vocational self-concepts in work roles”. At adolescence, the individual’s self-concept becomes comparatively stable but passes through some modification due to socio-environmental influences. Thus, employees derive satisfaction in life or work based on how they implement their self-concepts at work or other avenues of relationship. The life stage developmental model by Super (1990) comprises: “growth, exploration, establishment, maintenance (management), and decline (disengagement)”

2.3. Empirical Review

SN	Author (s)	TOPIC	Variables	Major findings
1	Dialoke, & Adighije (2018)	Determine the effect of career development on the employees' performance on Non-academic Staff of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike	career development and employees' performance	there is a positive and significant correlation between career development and the performance of the Non-academic Staff of the university
2	Irefin, & Mohammed (2014)	examined the effect of employee commitment on organizational performance with special interest in Coca Cola Nigeria Limited	employee commitment and organizational performance	there is a fairly high relationship between employee commitment and organizational performance;
3	Folorunso, Adewale, & Abodunde, (2014).	examined the impact of organizational commitment dimensions on employees' performance among academic staff of Oyo State owned tertiary institutions.	employee training and organizational performance	The findings indicated that there is a positive and significant influence of employee training on organizational performance
4	Oyeniya, Adeyemi & Olaoye (2017)	investigated the influence of organizational commitment on job performance among the employees in Nigerian hospitality industry	employee training on organizational performance	has negative but insignificant influence on job performance.
5	Brenyah (2019)	examined Organizational Support for Career Development and Its Influence on Employee Commitment in the Ghana Police Service	Employee Commitment and career development	Findings suggested that Organizational support for career development had significant impact on affective and normative commitment.
6	Maria-Dolores .Kwon, & Wong, (2017)	examined the impact of Employees' Commitment on Organizational Performance in Eravurpatru Divisional Secretariat	Employees' Commitment and Organizational Performance	The results of the study indicate that the Employees' Commitment are significantly related to Organizational Performance in Eravurpatru Divisional Secretariat
7	Dinku (2018)	determine the effects of employee commitment on performance of organization based on a case study of Arjo Didessa Sugar Factory	employee commitment and performance of organization	employees' commitments were found to have effects on the organizational performance in the study area
8	Ikoru & Nwosu (2017).	investigated the effects of strategic planning on organizational performance with Nigerian Bottling Company Enugu	strategic planning and organizational performance	The result of the analysis indicate that there is relationship between effective strategic planning and organizational performance
9	Adetayo. (2018).	examined the impact of strategic planning on organizational performance using a study of selected manufacturing organizations in Lagos, Nigeria	strategic planning and organizational performance	The findings reveals that there is a positive relationship between the use of strategic planning and organizational performance in today's corporate environment
10	Akinyele and Fasogbon.(2017).	examined the impact of strategic planning on organizational performance and survival	strategic planning and organizational performance	Strategic planning enhances better organizational performance

11	Olusanya, Awotungase, & Ohadebere (2016)	impact of effective Planning on Organizational Productivity using Sterling bank Nigeria Plc as a case study	Planning and Organizational Productivity	effective planning has a relationship with organizational productivity and that effective planning lead to employee's performance in an organization.
12	Monye, & Ibegbulem,(2018).	Analyzed the effect of strategic planning on organizational performance and profitability	employees' training, development and organizational performance	strategic planning enhances better organizational performance,
13	Owolabi, & Makinde,(2018).	examined the effects of Strategic Planning on Corporate Performance using Babcock University as the case study	Strategic Planning and Corporate Performance	The results of the hypotheses revealed that there is a significant positive correlation between strategic planning and corporate performance.
14	Muogbo (2017)	investigated the impact of strategic management on organizational growth and development of selected manufacturing firms in Anambra State	strategic management and organizational growth	strategic management is not yet a common business practice among manufacturing firms in Anambra State,
15	Omotayo, Olumuyiwa and Akinola (2018) .	evaluated the different factors that influence the choice of strategic planning adopted by banks in the country	strategic management and organizational growth	revealed that the factors influencing the choice of strategic planning adopted by banks in the country include technological environment
16	Njanja Maina, Kibet,. & Njagi (2017)	determined the effect of reward on employee performance at Kenya Power and Lighting Company (KPLC) Ltd	reward on employee performance	Their findings showed that cash bonus have no effect on employee performance
17	Olubusayo Ibidunni, & Olokundun,. (2014)	examined the effect of incentives packages on employees' attitudes towards work	incentives packages on employees' attitudes	there is strong correlation between the tested dependent variable and independent construct
18	Hameed, Ramzan, Zubair, Ali, &. Arslan (2017).	measured the impact of compensation on employee performance	of human capital development in organizational performance	The result shows from correlation analysis that all the independent variables have weak or moderate positive relationship to each
19	Bari, Arif, & Shoaib (2016)	study was to find out the impact of nonfinancial rewards on employee attitude	nonfinancial rewards and employee attitude	Their results showed that feedback to employees, freedom, career development plan, valuation of employees, learning programs, open & comfortable work environment and good supervisory relations have positively impacts on employee attitude and performance in the workplace.
20	Idemobi, Ngige, & Ofili (2017)	examined effect of reward system on organizational performance	reward system and organizational performance	The result shows that: organizations reward system has a significant effect on workers' performance;
21	Onuorah, Okeke, & Ibekwe,	examined the effect of compensation management and employee performance in Nigeria	compensation management and employee performance	compensation has no negative significance effect on employee performance in Nigeria

22	(2019) Ejumudo (2017)	organization examines pay reward system management and staff performance in Nigeria: using the Delta sate civil service as a focus State	system management and organizational performance	organization The findings of the study indicate that the incongruence of the pay reward system of the Delta state civil service and the central guiding principles of fairness
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METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

We adopted the descriptive survey design using the primary data collection method. With the aid of a structured close ended questionnaire on a five point Likert scale as the instrument for data collection, we distributed the copies of the questionnaire to respondents in the selected study area. (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2016).

3.2. Population of the Study

The population for the study comprises of students of Chukwuemka Odumegwu Ojukwu University (Uli Campus, Igbariam Campus and University Teaching Hospital Amaku), Nnamdi Azikwe University (University Main Campus and Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital; Nnewi) and Nwafor Orizu College of Education, Nsugbe. The total number of students of Nnamdi Azikiwe University is twenty-nine thousand, nine hundred and eighty-one (28981), (NAU Student Affairs Unit, 2022) while that of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University is thirteen thousand, two hundred and fifty(13250), (COOU, Student Affairs Unit,2022) and Nwafor Orizu College of Education Nsugbe is fifteen thousand, four hundred and seventy-nine (15,479), (NOCEN, Student Affairs Unit,2022) making it a total number of 57, 710 students.

Nnamdi Azikiwe University has few campuses but the researchers made use of the university main Campus and Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi as part of the size for the study. Also, the three campuses under Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University which are Igbariam Campus, Uli Campus and University Teaching Hospital Amaku were all taken into consideration. The main Campus of Nwafor Orizu College of Education Nsugbe was equally included in the study. Anambra state has a total of eight higher Education Institutions

3.3 Sample size determination

According to kerlinger (1973) simple random sampling is the method of drawing a portion of population or universe so that each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected. The population size of the study is fifty-seven thousand seven hundred and ten (57,710) students

For the fact that it is practically impossible to conveniently handle all the respondents of the selected institution in Anambra state, the researcher applied the statistical formula devised by Taro Yamane (1964), which states:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where

- n= Sample size of the study
- N = Population
- 1 = Constant value
- e = Errormargin assumed to be (5%)

Applying this formula, we have

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{57710}{1+57710(5\%)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{57710}{1+57710(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{57710}{1+105.58}$$

$$n = \frac{57710}{144.28}$$

Sample size = 369

Sampling Technique

The researcher adopted stratified random sampling. Using this method, stratification of the employees will be strictly based on their positions in university hierarchy: top, and middle management respectively. That is academic staff who are in level i, ii, senior and professors level were randomly selected. Thus random sampling ensures that units of the sample are selected on the basis of chance and all units have an equal chance of being included in the sample.

3.4 Sources of Data

In this study we used both primary and secondary data.

4. Primary Data

Primary source of data was through the in-depth interview, with audiotape recording where permission was granted. Furthermore, field-note was taken. Since, some data were sensitive, the privacy, confidentiality of respondents was protected throughout the processes of qualitative data collection. The location for the in-depth interview was the workplace of the respondents.

3.5. Method of Data Analysis

The completed transcripts were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 16.0 computer programme to determine recurring themes. Quotes gathered from the interviewees during case studies have been used to give meaning to the results. The technique of analysis was both theoretical and statistical in nature. With regard to theory, it was purely descriptive, comparative and analytical.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

In this section, the demographic features of the respondents such as gender, marital status, age bracket, educational qualification and are presented and analyzed. A total of three hundred and sixty-nine respondents were sampled and three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies questionnaire were retrieved 93.2% was the percentage rate of returned questionnaire. The results are presented in the table below.

4.1.1 Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	270	49.5	77.8	77.8
Female	77	14.1	22.2	100.0
Total	347	63.7	100.0	

Source: SPSS, Version, 2023

The above table reveals that the 77% of the respondents which represents ninety (270) persons were male respondents, while seventy (70) respondents which represent 22.2% were female respondents. By implication, male respondents were more than female respondents by 48% in our selected population sample for this study. The implication of this is to enable us to know the number of female and male that successfully returned their questionnaire.

4.1.2 Statues

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid MARRIED	122	22.4	35.2	35.2
SINGLE	225	41.3	64.8	100.0
Total	347	63.7	100.0	

Source: SPSS, Version, 2023

In the table above, out of the three hundred and forty-seven (347) respondents, one hundred and twenty-two (122) of the respondents, representing 35.2% are married while two hundred and twenty-five (225) respondents which represent 64.8percent are single. It is therefore glaring that the majority of the respondents are single as at the time of this study. Thus marital status table help us to know the number of single, married, and divorce respondents that answered the distributed questionnaires.

4.1.3 AGE

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 15-25	179	32.8	51.6	51.6
26-35	84	15.4	24.2	75.8
36-45	36	6.6	10.4	86.2
46-ABOVE	48	8.8	13.8	100.0
Total	347	63.7	100.0	

Source: SPSS, Version, 2023

Table 4.1.3 above depicted the age bracket of the respondents. The distribution shows that 51.6% of the respondents are between the age brackets of 15 to 25 years while 84 respondents representing 24.2% are within the age bracket of 26 - 35 years. On the same note, 10% of the respondents are within the age bracket of 31 - 45 years while the remaining respondents representing 13.8% are within the age bracket of 45 years and above.

4.2 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression result was employed to test the effect of independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in the tables below.

Table 4.2.1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.748 ^a	.560	.557	.27025	.560	218.637	2	344	.000	1.634

a. Predictors: (Constant), MOT, RWD

b. Dependent Variable: ORGP

Table 4.2.1 shows that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 56%. This implies that 56% of the variation in organizational performance is explained by variations in reward and motivation. This was supported by adjusted R² of 55.7%. In order to check for autocorrelation in the model, Durbin-Watson statistics was employed. Durbin-Watson statistics of 1.634 in table 3 shows that the variables in the model are not auto correlated and that the model is reliable for predications.

Table 4.2.2: ANOVA Result

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	31.936	2	15.968	218.637	.000 ^b
	Residual	25.124	344	.073		
	Total	57.061	346			

a. Dependent Variable: ORGP

b. Predictors: (Constant), MOT, RWD

The f-statistics value of 218.637 in table 4.2.2 with f-statistics probability of 0.002 shows that the independent variables has significant effect on dependent variables such as motivation and reward, can collectively explain the variations in Organizational Development

Table 5 Coefficients of the Model

T-statistics and probability value from the regression result are the effect of individual independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The summary of the result is presented in the table below.

Table 4.2.3 T-Statistics and Probability Value from the Regression Result Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	d Coefficients Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.198	.074		2.686	.008	-.344	-.053
	RWD	.616	.031	.745	2.996	.006	.556	.677
	MOT	.206	.018	.427	3.453	.000	.170	.241

a. Dependent Variable: ORGP

Source: Author’s Compilation from SPSS Version 21.0

Table 4.2.3 shows the coefficient of the individual variables and their probability values. reward variables have regression coefficient of 0.616 with a probability value of .006. This implies that planning have a positive and significant effect on Organizational performance of university students. Motivation has a regression coefficient of 0.206 with a probability value of 0.000 implying that Motivation variables has a positive and significant effect on Organizational performance

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

4.3.1 Test of Hypothesis One

HO₁: Reward has no significant effect on organizational development of tertiary institutions in Anambra state

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table 4.7 is used. Reward variables have a t-statistics of 2.996 and a probability value of 0.006 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that reward has significant effect on organizational performance of tertiary institutions in Anambra state. The study found that reward has significant positive effect on employee performance in selected local governments in Anambra state. This implies that improved training and development would translate to increased staff turnover, reduced cost of maintenance and equipment breakdown and lower compliants. It creates a less need for supervisor thereby enhancing employees output. Salah (2016) corroborates this finding by stating that, well reward and Organizational Performance are seen as the bedrock of any organization and institution. This means that, reward programs and carefully set development plans enhances skills and knowledge of employees which results in significant efficiency in workers productivity.

4.3.2 Test of Hypothesis Two

HO₂: Motivation has no significant effect on organizational development of tertiary institutions in Anambra state

Motivation has a t-statistics of 2.014 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypotheses which state Motivation has significant effect on organizational development of tertiary institutions in Anambra state. The study finds that Motivation has a significant positive effect on Organizational Performance in selected firm in Anambra State. This implies that Organization commitment provide motivation and propel employees to behave in ways that would lead to enhanced productivity. Alfandi and Alkawsawneh (2014) found that enriched Organization commitment is a significant factor that encourages employees as well as increase their zeal at work which results in enhanced Organization commitment and performance.

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary of the findings

This study examines the effect of reward and motivation on organizational Performance of tertiary institutions in Anambra state.

Reward has significant effect on Organizational Performance of tertiary institution in Anambra state. T-statistics of 2.996 and probability value of 0.006

Motivation has significant effect on Organizational Performance of tertiary institution in Anambra state. T-statistics of 3.453 and probability value of 0.000

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, the study on the effect of rewards and motivation on organizational performance of tertiary institutions in Anambra State reveals that effective reward systems and motivational strategies significantly enhance employee productivity, commitment, and job satisfaction. When academic and non-academic staff are adequately motivated through both monetary and non-monetary incentives, their performance improves, leading to better institutional efficiency, innovation, and student outcomes. Therefore, management of tertiary institutions in Anambra State should adopt fair, transparent, and performance-based reward structures to sustain high levels of motivation and overall organizational performance.

5.3 Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following are recommended:

- The study also recommends that management should provide effective incentive plan to their employees from time to time to boost their morale for enhanced productivity and performance. The reason is that bonuses will encourage them to put more effort in discharging their duties effectively.
- Management should do well to adopt on the spot praise as a medium for recognition and appreciation for hard work for promptness equal effectiveness.

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